

WELCOME TO SOUTH KOREA

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ABSTRACT

This article briefly describes South Korea's the most attractive and popular places for tourists all around the world. Country contains everything a traveler could want: history, entertainment and rest.

The recent popularity of Korean pop culture, often known as the "Korean wave", has increased the flow of tourists. While South Korea is not just pop singers, it is an attractive place because traditional Korean culture and modern culture coexist at the same time. First of all, Korea has a long history of becoming one of the popular countries in the world. There so many places, which survived a lot, but have been preserved in excellent condition. In this case, I find out the most attractive historical places of the three biggest cities in South Korea.

Gyeongbokgung Palace, located north of Gwangwamun Square, is one of the most famous landmarks in all of Korea due to its long history and floors. Gyeongbokgung Palace was completed in 1395 at the beginning of the Joseon dynasty under King Taegu. Gyeongbokgung, which means "Palace of the Blessed sky", was built in the

heart of Seoul, surrounded by Mount Bugaksan and Mount Namsan.^[1] Gyeongbokgung is interesting not only for connoisseurs of ancient Korean architecture and national color, but also for ordinary tourists. On the territory of the palace complex there are 330 buildings, in which there are 5792 rooms. In 1911, 10 buildings were damaged, which were completely demolished by the Japanese and a house for the Governor-General was built in their place. In addition, changing the guard each time attracts the attention of hundreds of tourists, where specially trained volunteers in bright national costumes of blue, red and yellow colors act as the royal guards, and each garment is unique and unlike the other.

In the early 15th century, King Daejeon ordered the construction of a new palace in a convenient location. To create the

complex, the Palace building office was created, consisting of a number of official and residential buildings located in the park, which was masterfully adapted to the uneven terrain of the 58-hectare site. The result is an exceptional example of Far Eastern palace architecture and design that blends harmoniously with the surrounding landscape.^[2] The most popular place for tourists is not the palace itself with its beautiful halls, but a secret park that begins behind the palace. Most often it is called the "back" park, or Pivon. Once it was the garden that became the starting point for the construction of a palace complex in this place. Its shady alleys and gazebos have become a favorite place for secluded royal walks. No courtiers were allowed in this garden, so the monarchs here could be alone with themselves or with their guests. The uniqueness of the secret park is that it does not break the surrounding mountainous terrain. Here, no one tried to level the territory and plant it with trees and shrubs in any particular style. When creating the garden, Korean architects tried to preserve and maintain the special beauty of this place, with its groves and rivers shrouded in fog and overgrown hills.

Puchon Village is not only a village, but an entire historical quarter of Seoul. It preserves the old traditional Korean Hanok houses. The village of Bukchon in Seoul is located next to Gyeongbokgung Palace. For sightseeing, the village is open and free for everyone all year round, seven days a week. If you look at the map, the village is located to the right of the palace and visiting these two places can be quite combined. For example, take a hanbok rental and walk around Gyeongbokgung,

and then through the village of Bukchon. Since ancient times, this area has been inhabited by educated people: scientists, poets, university professors, aristocrats, descendants of members of the royal family, as well as part of the service palace located nearby. Life was in full swing in the village of Bukchon. But even now, this area remains residential and one of the most expensive in Seoul.^[3]

The Haedong Yeonggungsa Temple in Busan is one of the few South Korean temples located on the seashore. This is a rare gem that is located outside the city to enjoy the stunning scenery. Haedong Yonggung, the only Korean temple usually built in the mountains, is located on a rocky shore. One side faces the churning waves of the East China Sea, the other is protected by mountains. The temple was founded by the famous monk Naong Hegeun, who lived at the junction of two great eras. He was the teacher of the last ruler of the Goryeo Dynasty (918-1392), from which the European name of the country is derived, and the supreme adviser (grand Master) of the Joseon era (Joseon Dynasty 1392-1910), which gave the name adopted in North Korea. It was Na Ong who contributed to the full spread of the foundations of Buddhism in Korea. From a small bridge, it is customary to throw coins for good luck. There is a stone staircase, 108 steps of which, according to one version, symbolize various human desires, and according to another: "108 sacred prayers of Buddhism".^[4]

In South Korea, in the hospitable Busan, there is a unique temple of Pomos. He was already 1300 years old. This ancient Buddhist building is still the residence of monks, but it opens its doors to visitors of all religious denominations. In addition,

the monastery has a magnificent wisteria park, where there are more than 500 varieties and varieties of this beautiful flowering plant. 55 thousand square meters have been allocated for planting. The park traces its history for 100 years. The best time to visit the park is in May, when the whole area turns into a colorful, fragrant oasis. All the buildings of Pomosa are unique, but Europeans are most captivated by the amazing "gate of one pillar" - Ilchumun. They lead to the monastery and are topped by a massive roof that actually rests on four powerful pillars. If you look at the building in profile, it seems as if the roof is supported by only one pillar.^[5]

Geumjung Mt., located on the top of the mountain of the same name, is the largest fortress in Korea. The exact time of its construction is unknown, but it is assumed that it was built in the era of the Three States. Initially, it was called "Dongrae Mountain Fortress", but then it was decided to name it after the mountain on which it is located.

Donghwasan Temple is located on the southern part of the Phalgonsan Mountains, which are 22 km away northeast of Daegu city. This temple was built by the monk Kykdal in the 15th year (493) of the reign of King Sojiwan of Silla. This temple was originally called Yugasa, but later during the reign of King Hyndok (826~836), the temple was rebuilt and given the name Tonhwasan. The name of the temple means "the temple where even in winter the pavonia blooms". The church was last rebuilt in 1732. This place is considered one of the largest places with stone works.^[6]

Buinsa Temple, a branch of Donghwasan Temple, was built in the seventh century

and enjoyed its influence during the Sheilla Dynasty as a prayer hall for Queen Seondok. There are many fragmentary stone works of art from that era, such as the stone bridge, cornerstone, reservoir, columns, etc. It remains above the ground of the temple, which has now been turned into a vineyard. There, about 300 meters to the south-east of this temple, there are preserved secondary building materials, such as the cornerstone, stone temples, stone lanterns. These remains confirm the historical importance of the Baines Temple as a precious piece of evidence supporting the size of the temple at that time.^[7]

The entire territory of the Pagyesa temple is surrounded by a dense forest and a transparent valley, which makes visitors feel out of this world. In the pagyesa temple area, 4 magnificent buildings, such as Jingdong-ru (Tower), Solson-dang, Chokmuk-dang, with Wontong-chon (Avalokiteshvara Hall) in the center, form the shape of the "Ural". Wang dong-chen (Avalokiteshvara Hall) is the central building, the mantle of the Great King Anjo was discovered here, and the Mokgwaneumbosang (wooden statue of the Buddhist goddess of Mercy) is also kept here.

If you are bored with history and your soul is asking for something modern, there is quite an extensive diversity of entertainment places. Though I think the most commonly-known would potentially be Escape Rooms, which located in Hongdae and Gangnam. In fact Escape Rooms is a physical adventure game in which the participants are locked in a themed room and have a set time limit to solve the clues needed to escape. You can choose from four different themed rooms.

According to reviews, the rooms are well decorated and the puzzles are intriguing. You won't know what it looks like until you get there, because photos are strictly forbidden. [8]

A subsequent category would be something like cafés. And the main characteristic of Korean cafés is that there is a fairly broad range of themed cafés such as Cat Café, Thanks Nature Café, Hello Kitty Café.

People in South Korea (as well as Japan) tend to live in very small apartments, in addition, having a pet is not very common in Asia, and many apartment buildings simply do not allow cats in the house. So the solution is cat cafes! The Cat Cafe is a place where people can come and spend a few hours with dozens of cute cats, pet them, play with them, feed them, or just watch her sleep. After entering the cat cafe, an entrance fee will be charged, and you will be advised to remove your shoes and disinfect your hands with antiseptic.

The unusual thing about the cafe is that real sheep live here, which are released from the arena a couple of times an hour: so that visitors can feed the animals with dry grass and, of course, take pictures. However, in the summer, when the sheep are sent to nature, visitors still come here, as the cafe is famous for its delicious waffles and a variety of tea and coffee. Nature Cafe boasts a relaxing atmosphere with lots of greenery. Art portraits of various animals hang on the walls, and one species stands out from the rest: sheep. In addition to small figurines and stuffed woolly animals, two well-groomed sheep live in the cafe's courtyard outside, where they socialize with patrons while enjoying coffee. The cafe's menu features drinks

made with natural sweeteners and delicious waffles, which are also popular with sheep, so don't eat them too close to the paddock.

If you are a fan of the Hello Kitty brand, then this cafe is definitely for you: the design of the room will please the eye, the baristas will draw you a kitty on a cappuccino, and you will also be able to see Hello Kitty in Hanbok. Walking up the stairs to the cafe, your heart will beat with excitement when you see a light pink house covered with trees. As you head upstairs, you are greeted by the subtle decorations of the Hello Kitty lawn. Stepping out onto the main balcony, you'll be enchanted by all the welcoming shades of pink and even the picture machine! The interior of the cafe is the cream of the crop, as the designers have definitely put their heart and soul into what could be a Hello Kitty dream home in Seoul. If you go upstairs, you will see her bedroom and various display cases with the image of the cat itself. [9]

In addition to cafés there are large mall, which consist of diverse mixture of shops. The main branch of Lotte Department Store is located in a prominent location in the Myeongdong shopping district. It is the largest department store in Korea, offering high-quality shopping to both Koreans and visitors. It is directly connected to Lotte Hotel Seoul, located next to Lotte Young Plaza in the heart of Seoul. Myeongdong is the largest shopping district in Korea, with more than 1.5 million shoppers visiting every day. Thus, Myeongdong plays an important role for foreign visitors to Korea and Seoul.

The building of the Shopping center "COEX", opened after reconstruction on November 27, 2014, has acquired a new

modified style, presented in the concept of Unfolding Sky (Open skyscraper), the design of which was designed by the world construction and architectural company Gensler (Gensler), maximizing the open space and the interconnection of objects in it. A special feature of the new concept of the complex is the creation of five huge open spaces, equipment for accounting for the flow of visitors, maximum illumination with natural light. The COEX Shopping Center combines lifestyle and fashion, beauty, famous boutiques, including global spa brands, and in the most crowded parts of the complex - multiple cafeterias and restaurants.

While you might think this mall got its name from Manhattan's famous commercial intersection, Times Square Mall has its own unique and historic history. Originally on the site of the Yeongdeungpo factory of the Kyung Sung Textile Company (much of which was destroyed due to Japanese colonization and the Korean War), this ultra-modern shopping mall was named Times Square to co-exist in harmony with its former owners. Opening its doors on September 16, 2009, it is currently one of the largest shopping malls in Seoul. The main atrium on the ground floor is considered the largest in Asia, with 2 bridges and plenty of space for a central event in the middle. Each month, atrium presents new cultural events with previous events, including musical performances by top K-pop stars, magic shows, experience zones, Special Markets, and the annual New Year's Countdown in Times Square. With Shinsegae Department Store, Kyobo Bookstore, CGV, E-Mart, Courtyard by Marriott, Seoul's largest Kolon Sporex, literally crowned with rooftop gardens,

Times Square Mall is a great place to spend the day. ^[10]

For South Korea, the most recognizable landmark and symbol of the capital is the Seoul Tower, located on the top of Mount Namsan. Previously, the Seoul Tower served as an automatic transmission of TV and radio waves, but now it has become a whole cultural space and a favorite vacation spot for citizens and foreign visitors who come here to admire the magnificent views of Seoul. The territory of Seoul Namsan Tower is divided into 2 large zones – Seoul Tower N (N Seoul Tower) and Seoul Tower Plaza (Seoul Tower Plaza), on each floor of which there are also many interesting places that are worth visiting. After climbing to the observation deck of the Seoul Tower, you will be able to see the whole of Seoul at a glance with the help of a special digital display. In order to get to the observation deck, you need to make a reservation in advance on the underground floor or in the Plaza and then use the elevator that will take you to this amazing place.

After climbing to the observation deck of Seoul Tower N, you will be able to see all of Seoul at a glance with the help of the private screen number. In order to get to the observation deck, you need to book a room on the underground floor or on the Square in advance, and then use the elevator that will take you to this amazing place. The National Museum of Korea is equipped with video and audio guide systems, so the entire exhibition can be seen in a short period of time. In total, visitors are offered 12 excursions. Designed guided tours in the museum for both adults and children. Every one of them speaks Korean, Chinese, Japanese and English.

Located near the city center, Lotte World Amusement Park in Seoul (South Korea) offers visitors a unique combination of classic attractions and theme parks with entertainment. Here you can test your courage in popular thrillers, for example, hitting the gyroscope with drops, or take a ride on the Flume train. Lotte World Park in Seoul is an ideal place for entertainment and sightseeing for both Koreans and foreign tourists. This is a theme park with many exciting attractions, an ice rink, and a folk museum. Lotte World in Seoul regularly hosts various parades. Lotte World is divided into 2 zones:

- Lotte World Adventure – World Themed Area;
- Magic Island-outdoor entertainment near Seokheonhosu Lake.

Jeju is the largest of the more than four thousand islands belonging to the Republic of Korea. It is also the most remote: the distance to the extreme southern point of the mainland is 90 km. Due to its isolation from the centers of civilization and its unique tropical appearance, the island has become a real find for tourists who rush here from different parts of the world. The mild maritime climate of Jeju (harmoniously combines with the unique natural landscape created by volcanic activity. And the island itself, one of the most beautiful in the East Asian region, is an extinct ancient volcano. Almost in the center is one of the natural attractions-Mount Hallasan, the highest point in South Korea, soaring into the sky at 1950 meters. Jeju-

an island and at the same time a special autonomous province of the Republic of Kazakhstan-was included in the list of UNESCO World Heritage Sites in 2007. And according to the results of the international competition held in 2011 by the Swiss New 7 Wonders Foundation, it was included in the rating of seven new wonders of the world.

Above all, if you are looking for a night adventure Itaewon is perfect place. Itaewon is a well-known district of Seoul, not only in the Korean capital. Such a small America in the heart of the city. Itaewon has a long history with the United States of America – it is here that the American military base is located, designed to protect South Korea from the invasion of North Korea.

And although this trip is not cheap for a significant part of our tourists. After all, only the flight itself will cost you a lot of money, but many say that it is worth it. After all, where else can you see an impressive number of skyscrapers adjacent to well-groomed, medieval pagodas of Buddhist temples and other attractions of South Korea. At the same time, depending on your preferences, tourism in South Korea can offer almost any entertainment, starting from the sandy beaches of the warm Sea of Japan and ending with the ski resorts of the mountainous part of the country. I can say you will never regret your decision to visit South Korea and will without any doubt want to come back again.

REFERENCES:

1. **Source:** Gyeongbokgung Palace

Source author: No author given

Source link: <https://www.theseoulguide.com/gyeongbokgung-palace/>

Date accessed: 18.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: This article provides some facts of Gyeongbokgung Palace and what exactly you can see if you will be there. I am going to discuss some information from this article in my paper.

2. **Source:** Changdeokgung Palace Complex

Source author: No author given

Source link: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/816/>

Date accessed: 18.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: This article provides description of Changdeokgung Palace (how it was built) and its history. The information in this article is related to some things I am going to write in my paper.

3. **Source:** Bukchon Hanok Village

Source author: Natalia Agiar

Source link: <https://mirnetesen.blogspot.com/2018/01/derevnya-bukchon-seul.html>

Date accessed: 18.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: This Russian article gives information about Bukchon Hanok Village, when and how it was built. I want to use some information provided in this article in my paper.

4. **Source:** Haedong Yonggungsa Temple

Source author: Aurelia Teslaru

Source link: <https://dailytravelpill.com/haedong-yonggungsa-temple-busan/>

Date accessed: 18.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: This article provides a brief overview of Haedong Yonggungsa Temple. Best time for visiting there. I would like to discuss some things from this article in my paper.

5. **Source:** A brief history of Beomeosa Temple

Source author: Phoebe Taylor

Source link: <https://theculturetrip.com/asia/south-korea/articles/a-brief-history-of-beomeosa-temple/>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: 26 March 2018

Info provided: This article presents a brief history of Beomesa Temple: its origins and the best way for visiting. It was written by a tourist, who was able to visit this temple. I would like to discuss some her words in my paper.

6. **Source:** Храм Тонхваса в Тэгу (동화사 (대구)) -

Source author: No author given

Source link: <http://www.koreatriptips.com/ru/tourist-attractions/336093>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: The web site gives an overview of temple, namely its history, its location and etc. I will discuss some information in my paper.

7. **Source:** Buinsa Temple

Source author: daegucity korea

Source link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=k6fWimhLehA>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: 05.01.2015

Info provided: The video clearly displays appearance of temple and its history by native person. And the information he gave is useful for my paper.

8. **Source:** Seoul Escaping Rooms

Source author: almostu/ Eiggod8

Source link: <https://www.tripadvisor.com/Attractions-g294197-Activities-c56-t208-Seoul.html>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: Web site provides full information about two escape room, which I am going to discuss in my paper.

9. **Source:** 15 Themed Cafes in Seoul that Are Too Awesome to Resist

Source author: Ting

Source link: <https://www.tripzilla.com/seoul-themed-cafes/54755>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: Mart 14th, 2017

Info provided: This article gives overview of 15 themed cafés in Seoul. I chose the interesting ones, which I am going to discuss in my paper.

10. Source: 9 Best Shopping Molls in Seoul

Source author: No author given

Source link: <https://www.hotels.com/go/south-korea/best-seoul-shopping-malls>

Data accessed: 23.04.2021

Date of publication: Not Available

Info provided: From 9 shopping malls, which described in this website, I chose the 3 big ones, which I will discuss in my paper.